

Effect of Nickel Substitution on Ammonia Gas Sensing property of Cobalt nano ferrite powders

S.Uday Bhasker*¹, Y.Veerawamy², B.Rakesh Goud¹, M V Ramana Reddy²

¹BS department, G.Narayanamma institute of technology and science, Hyderabad, TS, India

²Department of physics, Osmania University, Hyderabad

*sontuudaybhasker@gmail.com

Abstract

Atmospheric pollution with toxic gasses is a growing concern. Ferrites in general and nickel ferrite in particular, are reported to be a good sensor for ammonia gas. Here we report a facile and chemical additive-free method to synthesize chromium substituted cobalt nickel ferrite nano-particles (CR-CNFNP) $\text{Co}_{0.75}\text{Ni}_{0.25}\text{Fe}_{2-x}\text{Cr}_x\text{O}_4$ ($x=0, 0.20$) by auto combustion method. For the as prepared CR-CNFNP ceramic materials, physical and chemical characterization was done by X-ray diffraction (XRD) and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS). Diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS) was employed to study the optical band gap values. For sensing study, the high grade aluminum foil strip contacts were used as electrodes for the pelletized CR-CNFNP ceramic material and investigated for ammonia gas sensing response. The room temperature gas sensing studies show that chromium free sample shows increase in sensitivity with increasing ammonia concentration in air and chromium substituted sample shows decrease in sensitivity.

Key Words Spinel ferrite, Sol–gel combustion synthesis, Gas sensor, Nanocrystalas, $\text{Co}_{0.75}\text{Ni}_{0.25}\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_4$, chromium substitution